

Incidence Algebras and Labelings of Graph Structures

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Abstract: Ancykutty Joseph, *On Incidence Algebras and Directed Graphs*, IJMMS, 31:5(2002), 301-305, studied the incidence algebras of directed graphs. We have extended it to undirected graphs also in our earlier paper. We established a relation between incidence algebras and the labelings and index vectors introduced by R.H. Jeurissen in *Incidence Matrix and Labelings of a Graph*, Journal of Combinatorial Theory, Series B, Vol 30, Issue 3, June 1981, 290-301, in that paper. In this paper, we extend the concept to graph structures introduced by E. Sampathkumar in *On Generalized Graph Structures*, Bull. Kerala Math. Assoc., Vol 3, No.2, Dec 2006, 65-123.

Key Words: Graph structure, R_i -labeling, R_i -index vector, labelling matrix, index matrix, incidence algebra.

AMS(2010): 05C78, 05C50, 05C38, 06A11

§1. Introduction

Ancykutty Joseph introduced the concept of incidence algebras of directed graphs in [1]. She used the number of directed paths from one vertex to another for introducing the incidence algebras of directed graphs. Stefan Foldes and Gerasimos Meletiou [10] has discussed the incidence algebras of pre-orders also. This motivated us in our study on the incidence algebras of undirected graphs in [8]. We used the number of paths for introducing the concept of incidence algebras of undirected graphs. We also established a relation between incidence algebras and the labelings and index vectors of a graph as given by Jeurissen [12] (based on the works of Brouwer [2], Doob [9] and Stewart [15]) in that paper.

E. Sampathkumar introduced the concept of a graph structure in [13] as a generalization of signed graphs. In this paper, we extend the results of our paper on graphs to graph structures and prove that the collection of all R_i -labelings for the collection of all admissible R_i -index vectors, the collection of all R_i -labelings for the index vector 0 and the collection of all R_i -labelings for the index vector $\lambda_i j_i$, ($\lambda_i \in F$, F , a commutative ring j_i an all 1-vector) of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ are subalgebras of the incidence algebra $I(V, F)$. We also

¹Received February 15, 2011. Accepted August 2, 2011.

prove that the set of labeling matrices for all admissible index matrices of a graph structure is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$.

§2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, by a ring we mean an associative ring with identity. First We go through the definitions of commutative ring, partially ordered set, pre-ordered set etc. The following definitions are adapted from [16].

Definition 2.1 *A (left) A -module is an additive abelian group M with the operation of (left) multiplication by elements of the ring A that satisfies the following properties.*

- (i) $a(x + y) = ax + ay$ for any $a \in A, x, y \in M$;
- (ii) $(a + b)x = ax + bx$ for any $a, b \in A, x \in M$;
- (iii) $(ab)x = a(bx)$ for any $a, b \in A, x \in M$;
- (iv) $1x = x$ for an $x \in M$.

By an A -module, we mean a left A -module.

Definition 2.2 *A set $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ of elements of M is a basis for M if*

- (i) $a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n = 0$ for $a_i \in A$ only if $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_n = 0$ and
- (ii) M is generated by $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, i.e., M is the collection of all linear combinations of $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ with scalars from A .

A finitely generated module that has a basis is called free.

Definition 2.3 *An algebra A is a set over a field K with operations of addition, multiplication and multiplication by elements of K that have the following properties.*

- (i) A is a vector space with respect to addition and multiplication by elements of the field.
- (ii) A is a ring with respect to addition and multiplication.
- iii. $(\lambda a)b = a(\lambda b) = \lambda(ab)$ for any $\lambda \in K, a, b \in A$.

A subset S of an algebra A is called a subalgebra if it is simultaneously a subring and a subspace of A .

Definition 2.4([14]) *A set X with a binary relation \leq is a pre-ordered set if \leq is reflexive and transitive. If \leq is reflexive, transitive and antisymmetric, then X is a partially ordered set (poset).*

E. Spiegel and C.J. O'Donnell [14] defined incidence algebra as follows.

Definition 2.5([14]) *The incidence algebra $I(X, R)$ of the locally finite partially ordered set X over the commutative ring R with identity is $I(X, R) = \{f : X \times X \rightarrow R \mid f(x, y) =$*

0 if x is not less than or equal to y with operations given by

$$\begin{aligned}(f + g)(x, y) &= f(x, y) + g(x, y) \\ (f.g)(x, y) &= \sum_{x \leq z \leq y} f(x, z).g(z, y) \\ (r.f)(x, y) &= r.f(x, y)\end{aligned}$$

for $f, g \in I(X, R)$ with $r \in R$ and $x, y, z \in X$.

Ancykutty Joseph [1] established a relation between incidence algebras and directed graphs. The incidence algebra $I(G, Z)$ for digraph without cycles and multiple edges (G, \leq) representing the finite poset (V, \leq) is defined in [1] as follows.

Definition 2.6([1]) For $u, v \in V$, let $p_k(u, v)$ denote the number of directed paths of length k from u to v and $p_k(v, u) = -p_k(u, v)$. For $i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$, define $f_i, f_i^* : V \times V \rightarrow Z$ by $f_i(u, v) = p_i(u, v)$, $f_i^*(u, v) = -p_i(u, v)$. The incidence algebra $I(G, Z)$ of (G, \leq) over the commutative ring Z with identity is defined by $I(G, Z) = \{f_i, f_i^* : V \times V \rightarrow Z, i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$ with operations defined as

- (i) For $f \neq g, (f + g)(u, v) = f(u, v) + g(u, v)$;
- (ii) $(f.g)(u, v) = \sum_w f(u, w)g(w, v)$;
- (iii) $(zf)(u, v) = z.f(u, v) \forall z \in Z; f, g \in I(G, Z)$.

In [10], Stefan Foldes and Gerasimos Meletiou says about incidence algebra of pre-order as follows.

Definition 2.7([10]) Given a field F , the incidence algebra $A(\rho)$, of a pre-ordered set (S, ρ) , $S = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ over F is the set of maps $\alpha : S^2 \rightarrow F$ such that $\alpha(x, y) = 0$ unless $x \rho y$. The addition and multiplication in $A(\rho)$ are defined as matrix sum and product.

Replacing field F by a commutative ring R with identity and following the definition of Foldes and Meletiou[10], we obtained in graphs [8] an analogue of the incidence algebra of a directed graph given by Ancykutty Joseph[1].

Theorem 2.1([8]) Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph without cycles and multiple edges with V and E finite. For $u, v \in V$, let $f_i(u, v)$ be the number of paths of length i between u and v . Then $\{f_i\}$ is an incidence algebra of (G, ρ) denoted by $I(G, Z)$ over the commutative ring Z with identity.

§3. Graph Structure and Incidence Algebra

We recall some basic definitions on graph structure given by E. Sampathkumar[13].

Definition 3.1([13]) $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ is a graph structure if V is a non empty set and R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k are relations on V which are mutually disjoint such that each $R_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, is symmetric and irreflexive.

If $(u, v) \in R_i$ for some $i, 1 \leq i \leq k$, (u, v) is an R_i -edge. R_i -path between two vertices u and v consists only of R_i -edges. G is $R_1 R_2 \cdots R_k$ connected if G is R_i -connected for each i .

We define $R_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}$ -path, $1 \leq r \leq k$, in a similar way as follows.

Definition 3.2 A sequence of vertices x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n of V of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ is an $R_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}$ -path, $1 \leq r \leq k$, if $R_{i_1}, R_{i_2}, \dots, R_{i_r}$ are some among R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k which are represented in it.

Note that the above definition matches with the concepts introduced in [4] by the authors.

Theorem 3.1 Let $f_i^j(u, v)$ be the number of R_i -paths of length j between u and $f_i^{j*}(u, v) = -f_i^j(u, v)$. $I_{R_i}(G, Z) = \{f_i^j, f_i^{j*} : V \times V \rightarrow Z, i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ is an incidence algebra over Z .

Proof Let f_i^r and f_i^s be R_i -paths of length r and s respectively. For $f_i^r \neq f_i^s \in I_{R_i}(G, Z)$, define $((f_i^r + f_i^s)(u, v)) =$ number of R_i -paths of length either r or s between u and $v = f_i^r(u, v) + f_i^s(u, v)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (f_i^r \cdot f_i^s)(u, v) &= \text{number of } R_i\text{-paths of length } r + s \text{ between } u \text{ and } v \\ &= \sum_{w:(u,w) \in R_i, (w,v) \in R_i} f_i^r(u, w) f_i^s(w, v). \end{aligned}$$

$(z f_i^r)(u, v) = z \cdot f_i^r(u, v) \forall z \in Z; f_i^r, f_i^s \in I_{R_i}(G, Z)$ (The operations are extended in the usual way if either or both are elements of the form f_i^{r*}).

So $I_{R_i}(G, Z)$ is an incidence algebra over Z . \square

Note 1. We may also consider another type of incidence algebras. Let $f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l(u, v)$ be the number of $R_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}$ paths of length l between u and v and $f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^{l*}(u, v) = -f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l(u, v)$. Then $I_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}(V, Z) = \{f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l, f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^{l*} : V \times V \rightarrow Z, i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ with operations defined as follows is another subalgebra over Z .

$$(i) (f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l + f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^m)(u, v) = f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l(u, v) + f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^m(u, v).$$

$$(ii) (f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l \cdot f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^m)(u, v) = \sum_{w:(u,w), (w,v) \in \bigcup_{i=i_1}^{i_r} R_i} f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l(u, w) f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^m(w, v).$$

(iii) $(z f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l)(u, v) = z \cdot f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l(u, v) \forall z \in Z; f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l, f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^m \in I_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}(G, Z)$. (The operations are extended in the usual way if either or both are elements of the form f_i^{r*}).

Thus $I_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}(V, Z)$ is an incidence algebra over Z .

Note 2. Another possibility is to consider a subalgebra consisting of various paths of the type $R_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}$ with all of $i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r$ being different from $j_1 j_2 \cdots j_s$ for any two $u-v$ paths $f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}$ and $f_{j_1 j_2 \cdots j_s}$. Let $f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l, f_{m_1 m_2 \cdots m_s}^m$ be $R_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}$ and $R_{j_1 j_2 \cdots j_s}$ -paths of length l and m respectively. Define

$$(f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r}^l + f_{j_1 j_2 \cdots j_s}^m)(u, v) = f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r j_1 j_2 \cdots j_s}^l(u, v) + f_{i_1 i_2 \cdots i_r j_1 j_2 \cdots j_s}^m(u, v),$$

$$(f_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_r}^j \cdot f_{j_1 j_2 \dots j_s}^j)(u, v) = \sum_{w: (u, w), (w, v) \in \bigcup_{i=i_1}^{i_r} R_i} f_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_r}^l(u, w) f_{j_1 j_2 \dots j_s}^m(w, v),$$

$$(z f_{l_1 l_2 \dots l_r}^l)(u, v) = z \cdot f_{l_1 l_2 \dots l_r}^l(u, v),$$

$$I_{path}(V, Z) = \{f, f^* : V \times V \rightarrow Z\},$$

where f is an $R_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_r}$ -path, $i_1, i_2, \dots, i_r \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, $1 \leq r \leq k$ and $f^* = -f$. (The operations are extended in the usual way if either or both are elements of the form f^*).

Thus $I_{path}(V, Z)$ is an incidence algebra over Z .

§4. R_i -labelings and Incidence Algebra

Now consider R_i -labelings and R_i -index vectors of G . We recall the concepts of R_i -labelings and R_i -index vectors introduced in [5].

Definition 4.1 ([5]) *Let F be an abelian group or a ring and $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ be a graph structure with vertices v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{p-1} and q_i number of R_i -edges. A mapping $r_i : V \rightarrow F$ is an R_i -index vector with components $r_i(v_0), r_i(v_1), \dots, r_i(v_{p-1})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ and a mapping $x_i : R_i \rightarrow F$ is an R_i -labeling with components $x_i(e_i^1), x_i(e_i^2), \dots, x_i(e_i^{q_i})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$.*

An R_i -labeling x_i is an R_i -labeling for the R_i -index vector r_i iff $r_i(v_j) = \sum_{e_r \in E_i^j} x_i(e_r)$, where

E_i^j is the set of all R_i -edges incident with v_j . R_i -index vectors for which an R_i -labeling exists are called admissible R_i -index vectors.

Now we prove some results on R_i -labellings and incidence algebras. For that, first we recall the operations of addition and scalar multiplication mentioned in [5].

$$(r_i^1 + r_i^2)(v_j) = r_i^1(v_j) + r_i^2(v_j),$$

$$(f r_i^1)(v_j) = f r_i^1(v_j),$$

$$(x_i^1 + x_i^2)(e_j) = x_i^1(e_j) + x_i^2(e_j),$$

$$(f x_i^1)(e_j) = f x_i^1(e_j).$$

Now we define multiplication as follows.

Definition 4.2 *Let r_i^1, r_i^2 be R_i -index vectors and x_i^1, x_i^2 be R_i -labelings of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$.*

$$(r_i^1 \cdot r_i^2)(v_l) = \sum_{s: (v_l, v_s) \in R_i} r_i^1(v_l) r_i^2(v_s)$$

$$(x_i^1 \cdot x_i^2)(v_l, v_m) = 2 \cdot \sum_{s: (v_l, v_s) \in R_i, (v_s, v_m) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_l, v_s) x_i^2(v_s, v_m) \text{ (Multiplication by 2 is to ad-}$$

just the duplication due to symmetric property of R_i -edges).

Now we prove that with respect to these operations, the set of all R_i -labelings for all admissible R_i -index vectors is a subalgebra of the incidence algebra $I(V, F)$.

Theorem 4.1 *The set of R_i -labelings for all admissible R_i -index vectors of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ is a subalgebra of $I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$ where A_i is the collection of all admissible R_i -index vectors.*

Proof Let $I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$ be the collection of R_i -labelings for elements of A_i . Let $x_i^1, x_i^2 \in I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$. Then there exist $r_i^1, r_i^2 \in F$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} r_i^1(v_j) &= \sum_{p:(v_j, v_p) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_p) \quad \text{and} \quad r_i^2(v_j) = \sum_{p:(v_j, v_p) \in R_i} x_i^2(v_j, v_p). \\ (r_i^1 + r_i^2)(v_j) &= r_i^1(v_j) + r_i^2(v_j) = \sum_{p:(v_j, v_p) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_p) + \sum_{p:(v_j, v_p) \in R_i} x_i^2(v_j, v_p) \\ &= \sum_{p:(v_j, v_p) \in R_i} (x_i^1 + x_i^2)(v_j, v_p). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $x_i^1 + x_i^2$ is an R_i -labeling for $(r_i^1 + r_i^2)$, i.e., $x_i^1 + x_i^2 \in I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$.

$$\begin{aligned} (r_i^1 \cdot r_i^2)(v_j) &= \sum_{s:(v_j, v_s) \in R_i} r_i^1(v_j) r_i^2(v_s) \\ &= \sum_{s:(v_j, v_s) \in R_i} \left[\sum_{l:(v_j, v_l) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_l) \sum_{m:(v_s, v_m) \in R_i} x_i^2(v_s, v_m) \right] \\ &= 2. \sum_{s:(v_j, v_s) \in R_i} \sum_{m:(v_s, v_m) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_s) x_i^2(v_s, v_m) \\ &= \sum_{n:(v_j, v_n) \in R_i} (x_i^1 x_i^2)(v_j, v_n) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $x_i^1 \cdot x_i^2$ is an R_i -labeling for $r_i^1 \cdot r_i^2$, i.e., $x_i^1 \cdot x_i^2 \in I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$.

$$\begin{aligned} (f r_i^1)(v_j) &= f \cdot r_i^1(v_j) \\ &= f \cdot \sum_{n:(v_j, v_n) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_n) \\ &= \sum_{n:(v_j, v_n) \in R_i} f x_i^1(v_j, v_n) \\ &= \sum_{n:(v_j, v_n) \in R_i} (f x_i^1)(v_j, v_n) \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $f x_i^1 \in I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$. Hence $I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V, F)$. \square

For the next few results, we require results from our previous papers [5] and [7].

Theorem 4.2([5]) *If F is an integral domain, the R_i -labelling of G for the R_i -index vector 0 form a free F -module.*

Theorem 4.3([7]) *Let F be an integral domain. Then $S_i(G)$, the collection of R_i -labelings for $\lambda_i j_i, \lambda_i \in F, j_i$ an all 1-vector, is a free F -module.*

Theorem 4.4 *The set of R_i -labellings for $\lambda_i j_i, \lambda_i \in F, j_i$ an all 1 vector of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ forms a subalgebra of the incidence algebra $I(V, F)$.*

Proof Let $I_{L(\lambda_i)}(V, F)$ be the collection of R_i -labelings for $\lambda_i j_i$. Let $x_i^1, x_i^2 \in I_{L(\lambda_i)}(V, F)$. Then there exist $\lambda_i^1, \lambda_i^2 \in F$ such that

$$\lambda_i^1(v_j) = \sum_{p:(v_j v_p) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_p) \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_i^2(v_j) = \sum_{p:(v_j v_p) \in R_i} x_i^2(v_j, v_p).$$

By Theorem 4.3, $\lambda_i j_i$ is an F -module. Hence it is enough if we prove that $x_i^1.x_i^2$ is an R_i -labeling for $(\lambda_i^1.\lambda_i^2)j$

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda_i^1.\lambda_i^2)(v_j) &= \sum_{s:(v_j v_s) \in R_i} \lambda_i^1(v_j)\lambda_i^2(v_s) \\ &= \sum_{s:(v_j v_s) \in R_i} \left[\sum_{l:(v_j v_l) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_l) \sum_{m:(v_s v_m) \in R_i} x_i^2(v_s, v_m) \right] \\ &= 2. \sum_{s:(v_j v_s) \in R_i, (v_s v_n) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_s)x_i^2(v_s, v_n) \\ &= \sum_{n:(v_j v_n) \in R_i} (x_i^1 x_i^2)(v_j, v_n) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $x_i^1.x_i^2$ is an R_i -labeling for $\lambda_i^1.\lambda_i^2 = \lambda_i^3$. i.e., $x_i^1.x_i^2 \in I_{L(\lambda_i)}(V, F)$. Hence $I_{L(\lambda_i)}(V, F)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V, F)$. \square

Theorem 4.5 *The set of R_i -labelings for 0 of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ forms a subalgebra of the incidence algebra $I(V, F)$.*

Let $I_{L(0_i)}(V, F)$ be the collection of all R_i -labelings for 0. By Theorem 4.2, the collection is an F -module. So it is enough if we prove that $x_i^1.x_i^2 \in I_{L(0_i)}(V, F) \forall x_i^1, x_i^2 \in I_{L(0_i)}(V, F)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n:(v_j v_n) \in R_i} (x_i^1.x_i^2)(v_j, v_n) &= 2. \sum_{n:(v_j v_n) \in R_i} \left[\sum_{s:(v_j v_s) \in R_i, (v_s v_n) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_s)x_i^2(v_s, v_n) \right] \\ &= \sum_{s:(v_j v_s) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_s) \left[\sum_{n:(v_s v_n) \in R_i} x_i^2(v_s, v_n) \right] \\ &= \sum_{s:(v_j v_s) \in R_i} x_i^1(v_j, v_s).0(v_s) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $x_i^1.x_i^2$ is an R_i -labeling for 0. i.e., $x_i^1.x_i^2 \in I_{L(0_i)}(V, F)$. So $I_{L(0_i)}(V, F)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V, F)$. \square

§5. Labeling Matrices and Incidence Algebras

We now establish the relation between labeling matrices and incidence algebras. For that first we recall the concepts of labeling matrices and index matrices of a graph structure introduced by the authors in [6].

Definition 5.1([6]) *Let F be an abelian group or a ring. Let R_i be an R_i -index vector and x_i be an R_i -labeling for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Then*

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & x_2 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & 0 & \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & & \cdot & & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & & & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & x_k \end{bmatrix}$$

is a labeling matrix and

$$r = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & r_2 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot & 0 \\ \cdot & 0 & \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & & \cdot & & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & & & \cdot & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & r_k \end{bmatrix}$$

is an index matrix for the graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$.

$$x : \begin{bmatrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ R_k \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow F^k$$

is a labeling for $r : V^k \rightarrow F^k$ if $\sum_{m \in E_s} x_i(m) = r_i(x_s)$ for $s = 0, 1, \dots, p-1; i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. If r_i is an admissible R_i -index vector $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, then r is called an admissible index matrix for G .

Now we establish some relations between these and incidence algebras.

Theorem 5.1 *The set of labeling matrices for all admissible index matrices of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$.*

Proof Let $I_{L(A)}(V^k, F^k)$ be the set of all labeling matrices for the elements of A , the set of all admissible index matrices. Let $x_1, x_2 \in I_{L(A)}(V^k, F^k)$. Then $x_i^1, x_i^2 \in I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$, the set of all R_i -labelings for the elements of the set A_i of all admissible R_i -index vectors for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Then as proved in Theorem 4.1, $x_i^1 + x_i^2, x_i^1 \cdot x_i^2, f x_i^1 \in I_{L(A_i)}(V, F)$ where $f \in F$. Hence $x^1 + x^2, x^1 \cdot x^2, f x^1$ are labelings for some $r^1 + r^2, r^1 \cdot r^2, f r^1$ respectively. i.e., $x^1 + x^2, x^1 \cdot x^2, f x^1 \in I_{L(A)}(V^k, F^k)$. So $I_{L(A)}(V^k, F^k)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$. \square

Theorem 5.2 *The set of labeling matrices for ΛJ with*

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & . & . & . & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 & . & . & 0 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & . & . & 0 & \lambda_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad J = \begin{bmatrix} j_1 & 0 & . & . & . & 0 \\ 0 & j_2 & 0 & . & . & 0 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & . & . & 0 & j_k \end{bmatrix},$$

j_i , an all 1-vector for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$.

Proof Let $I_{L(\Lambda)}(V^k, F^k)$ be the set of all labeling matrices for the index matrix Λ . Let $x_1, x_2 \in I_{L(\Lambda)}(V^k, F^k)$. Then $x_i^1, x_i^2 \in I_{L(\lambda_i)}(V, F)$, the set of all R_i -labellings for λ_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Then as proved in Theorem 4.4, $x_i^1 + x_i^2, x_i^1 \cdot x_i^2, f x_i^1 \in I_{L(\lambda_i)}(V, F)$ where $f \in F$. Hence $x^1 + x^2, x^1 \cdot x^2, f x^1$ are labelings for $\Lambda^1 + \Lambda^2, \Lambda^1 \cdot \Lambda^2, f \Lambda^1$ respectively, i.e., $x^1 + x^2, x^1 \cdot x^2, f x^1 \in I_{L(\Lambda)}(V^k, F^k)$. So $I_{L(\Lambda)}(V^k, F^k)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$. \square

Theorem 5.3 *The set of labeling matrices for 0 of a graph structure $G = (V, R_1, R_2, \dots, R_k)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$.*

Proof Let $I_{L(0)}(V^k, F^k)$ be the set of all labeling matrices for the index matrix 0. Let $x_1, x_2 \in I_{L(0)}(V^k, F^k)$. Then $x_i^1, x_i^2 \in I_{L(0_i)}(V, F)$, the set of all R_i -labellings for 0 for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Then as proved in Theorem 4.5, $x_i^1 + x_i^2, x_i^1 \cdot x_i^2, f x_i^1 \in I_{L(0_i)}(V, F)$ where $f \in F$. Hence $x^1 + x^2, x^1 \cdot x^2, f x^1$ are labelings for $0 + 0 = 0, 0 \cdot 0 = 0, f 0 = 0$ respectively, i.e., $x^1 + x^2, x^1 \cdot x^2, f x^1 \in I_{L(0)}(V^k, F^k)$. So $I_{L(0)}(V^k, F^k)$ is a subalgebra of $I(V^k, F^k)$. \square

References

- [1] Ancykuty Joseph, On incidence algebras and directed graphs, *Internat. J. Math. and Math. Sc.*, 31:5(2002),301-305.
- [2] Brouwer, A.E., A note on magic graphs, Report ZN 47/72(Internal communication), 1972, Mathematisch Centrum, Amsterdam.
- [3] Dinesh, T. & Ramakrishnan, T.V., On generalized fuzzy graph structures, *Appl. Math. Sc.*, 5(4)(2011), 173-180.
- [4] Dinesh, T. & Ramakrishnan, T.V., Fuzzy graph structures - a generalized approach, accepted for publication in *Adv. Theoretical and Appl. Math.*
- [5] Dinesh, T. & Ramakrishnan, T.V., R_i -labellings and R_i -index vectors of a graph structure, *Adv. and Appl. in Discrete Math.*, 7(1)(2011), 63-82.
- [6] Dinesh, T. & Ramakrishnan, T.V., Labelling matrices and index matrices of a graph structure (Communicated).
- [7] Dinesh, T. & Ramakrishnan, T.V., Modules of labeling matrices for 0 and ΛJ of a graph structure, *Internat. J. Combin. Graph Theory and Appl.*, 3(2) (2010), 61-80.
- [8] Dinesh, T. & Ramakrishnan, T.V., Labelings of graphs and incidence algebras, to appear in *Internat. J. Contemp. Math. Sc.*, 6(26)(2011), 1253 - 1259.

- [9] Doob, M., Generalizations of magic graphs, *J. Combin. Theory*, Ser. B17(1974), 205-217.
- [10] Foldes, S. & Meletioui, G., On incidence algebras and triangular matrices, Rutcor Research Report 35-2002, November 2002, Rutgers Center for Operations Research, Rutgers University, New Jersey.
- [11] Harary, F., *Graph Theory*, Narosa Pub. House, 1995.
- [12] Jeurissen, R.H., Incidence matrix and labelings of a graph, *J. Combin. Theory*, Ser. B, Vol 30, Issue 3, June 1981, 290-301.
- [13] Sampathkumar, E., Generalized graph structures, *Bull. Kerala Math. Assoc.*, Vol 3, No.2, Dec 2006, 65-123.
- [14] Spiegel, E. & O'Donnell, C.J., *Incidence Algebras*, Marcel Dekker Inc., 1997.
- [15] Stewart, B.M., Magic graphs, *Canad. J. Math.*, 18(1966), 1031-1059.
- [16] Vinberg, E.B., *A Course in Algebra*, Graduate Studies in Mathematics, Vol 56, American Mathematical Society, 2009.